

Studies on the Conductance of Zinc Ferrocyanide Sol during Slow Coagulation by Electrolytes

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The specific conductance of zinc ferrocyanide sol, observed during the slow coagulation in presence of KCl, BaCl₂, and AlCl₃, has been studied in comparison with that of the aqueous potassium ferrocyanide acting as the dispersion medium (the so-called intermicellar liquid), being of the same conductance as that of the sol. On addition of the electrolyte, the maximum changes in conductance and in pH have been observed to occur immediately, indicating that ion-exchange phenomenon like adsorption during slow coagulation is an instantaneous process.

In continuation of our previous publications^{1,2} we have extended our studies on the changes in the conductance and pH of zinc ferrocyanide sol during the slow coagulation by three different electrolytes, viz., KCl, BaCl₂, and AlCl₃. The interesting observations obtained are recorded in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

By trial experiments the optimum proportion of zinc sulphate to potassium ferrocyanide solutions for the formation of stable zinc ferrocyanide sol was determined and the ratio was found to be 2:3. The sol, thus prepared, was dialysed against distilled water till free of potassium ferrocyanide.

Experimental procedures for the determination of the specific conductance of the sol, strength of the intermicellar liquid, and the amount of electrolytes required to coagulate the sol as also the changes in pH were exactly the same as recorded by Ouseph *et al.*²

The changes in conductance and in pH were studied from the curves to derive some conclusions regarding the mechanism of slow coagulation of zinc ferrocyanide sol.

DISCUSSION

The observations on the changes in conductance and in pH of the sol with respect to the intermicellar liquid, after addition of electrolytes, are noted below.

The conductance of the sol with the coagulating electrolyte is lower than that of the sol alone in all cases except that of KCl where it is greater (vide curves No. 1, 2, and 3). The same observation was made by Ouseph *et al.* in the case of copper ferrocyanide sol.

The conductance of the intermicellar liquid coupled with that of the coagulating electrolyte is in all cases greater than that of the sol having the same amount of electrolyte except in the case of AlCl₃ where it is lower (curves 1 to 3a).

1. Chaturvedi and Bhattacharya, *this Journal*, 1964, 31, 133.
2. Ouseph *et al.*, *Koll. Z. Polymers*, 1963, 169, 147.

The conductance of the sol+electrolyte shoots up instantaneously in the case of KCl and then falls slightly (vide Fig. 1). In the case of $BaCl_2$ and $AlCl_3$, there is a fall in conductance in the first instance and afterwards it attains a constancy with a further gradual fall (vide curves No. 2 and 3). Copper ferrocyanide sol² showed similar changes. In Figs. 1-3 sol taken was 5g./litre.

FIG. 1.

When the intermicellar liquid is mixed with KCl, the conductance shoots up instantaneously, approaching to constancy with a further gradual rise. With $BaCl_2$, there is a fall in conductance in the first instance and afterwards this conductance approaches to a constancy with a further gradual fall. In the case of $AlCl_3$, there is a gradual rise in conductance, reaching to a constancy after the fall in the first instance (vide curves No. 1a, 2a and 3a).

The pH of the sol with electrolyte in all stages of coagulation is lower than that of the pH values of the intermicellar liquid mixed with the same amount of electrolytes (vide curves No. 4 to 6a). The reverse observations were obtained in the case of copper ferrocyanide sol¹.

FIG. 2

The pH of the sol on addition of KCl rises first and then approaches to a constancy with a further gradual rise. But in the case of BaCl₂ and AlCl₃, the pH first falls and then rises gradually till it reaches to a constant value.

When KCl is added to the sol, there may be an adsorption of the K⁺ ions of the electrolyte and after this adsorption there may be liberation of other ions having greater ionic mobility. These ions may be responsible for the increase in conductance. But in the case BaCl₂ and AlCl₃, the conductance is diminished, indicating a different behaviour of KCl towards zinc ferrocyanide sol, compared with that of BaCl₂ and AlCl₃. In the case of BaCl₂ and AlCl₃, surface reaction may be more predominant, resulting in the formation of feebly dissociated compounds, such as Ba or Al ferrocyanide, which may be responsible for the decrease in conductance.

The increase in pH of the sol on addition of KCl may be due to instantaneous hydrolysis of the intermediate compound formed by the surface reaction, resulting in the lowering of H^+ -ion concentration. But in the cases of $BaCl_2$ and $AlCl_3$, the effect is reverse. It seems that on addition of $BaCl_2$ or $AlCl_3$, H^+ ions are released from the double layer, resulting in the lowering of pH . Simultaneously surface reactions give rise to the formation of surface compounds, which may not be hydrolysed instantaneously as in the case of KCl , but may hydrolyse after a certain interval, resulting in the formation of Ba or Al hydroxide. Such compounds would obviously react with H^+ ions and hence pH would rise after a fall (vide curves No. 5 and 6).

The behaviour of KCl , $BaCl_2$, and $AlCl_3$ towards zinc ferrocyanide sol was found to be almost identical with that of copper ferrocyanide sol². The slight variation may be due to the difference in the ionic mobility of copper and zinc ions and the surface reactivity of the two sols.

On adding the electrolyte, the maximum changes in conductance and in pH have been found almost to take place immediately (vide adjoining curves), which shows that ion-exchange phenomenon like adsorption during slow coagulation is an instantaneous process.

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